

then incubated under $1400\mu\text{Em}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ at 35°C for 6 d. Treated leaves were divided into five grades based on the degree of green lost, with grades I and II being considered tolerant (see table).

Somaclonal variants have great differences in their responses to shading and photooxidative stresses (see table). Somaclonal variants with double tolerance

were obtained for both shade- and photooxidation-tolerant parent 02428 (such as 02428h and 02428hong), from photooxidation-tolerant but shade-sensitive parent Zhongguo 91 (such as CX-1), and from sensitive parent 842 to both shade and photooxidation-tolerant (such as 84202-chou 10).

The variants with double sensitivity may be particularly useful for improving culti-

vars with good agronomic characters but sensitivity to light stresses. Frequency of variants with double sensitivity or with either tolerance for shade or photooxidation from double-sensitive parents is higher, however, than that for variants with double tolerance. ■

Biochemical identification and genetic analysis of molybdenum cofactor mutants in rice

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The molybdenum cofactor (MoCo) prosthetic group is essential for the activity of molybdo enzymes, such as nitrate reductase (NR), xanthine dehydrogenase (XDH), and

sulfite oxidase. However, very little information is available on the MoCo biosynthetic pathway in rice. We report the biochemical identification and genetic analysis of MoCo-deficient mutants in rice to provide genetic information on this pathway.

Four MoCo-deficient mutants (*cnx* mutants), C25, C27, C32, and C33, were isolated as chlorate-resistant mutants from 100,000 M_2 seedlings. Biochemical analysis showed that NADH-, NADPH-NR, XDH activities, and MoCo biosynthesis abilities (MoCo activities) were deficient in these four mutants, indicating they were MoCo-deficient types (Table 1).

The *cnx* mutants could be divided into two groups: one that could recover NR activity by adding molybdate in growth medium and one that could not. To classify our *cnx* mutants, their 7-d-old seedlings were treated with Kimura's B solution containing 0.5 mM Na_2MoO_4 for 2 d. Molybdate treatment did not recover NADH-NR activity in C25 but did so in C27, C32, and C33; the activity was double that of the control (Table 1). We also investigated the tungstate sensitivity in the mutants because it has been reported that a tungstate-sensitive group exists among *Arabidopsis thaliana* *cnx* mutants. We hydroponically cultured the mutants and their wild type IR30 with culture medium containing 0.1, 1, or 10 mM Na_2MoO_4 for 7 d. In all treatments, no significant differences occurred between the mutants and IR30 in seedling height and root length. We therefore conclude that the four *cnx* mutants do not belong to the tungstate-sensitive group (Table 1).

Derived from the four cross combinations between *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30, the chlorate resistance in F_2 populations had a segregation of 3:1 wild type: mutant phenotype, indicating a single recessive gene controls each mutation (Table 2).

The allelism test, using the three F_2 populations derived from the crosses between the four *cnx* mutants, indicated that the three mutant genes of C27, C32, and C33 are located at the same locus, and that the genes of C25 and these three mutants are located at different loci (Table 2). This result coincides with the phenotypic classification based on the restoration of NADH-NR activity by molybdate as mentioned above. Thus, we conclude that at least two loci are involved in the MoCo biosynthetic pathway in rice. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of the four *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30.

Line	NADH-NR activity ^a		NADPH-NR activity ^a	MoCo activity ^b	XDH	Chlorate resistant	Tungstate sensitive
	Control	+0.5 mM Na_2MoO_4					
IR30	870.2	432.4 (49) ^c	11.3	3.8	+ ^d	S ^e	R ^e
C25	0.0	0.0 (0)	0.0	0.0	-	R	R
C27	170.0	465.4 (273)	0.3	1.4	δ	R	R
C32	207.6	467.7 (225)	1.1	1.6	δ	R	R
C33	194.6	517.8 (266)	0.0	0.4	δ	R	R

^an mol $\text{NO}_2^- \text{min}^{-1} \text{g fresh weight}^{-1}$, ^bn mol $\text{NO}_2^- \text{min}^{-1} \text{mg protein}^{-1}$. ^cPercentage of control, ^{c+} = XDH activity; δ = very low XDH activity; - = no XDH activity. ^eS = sensitive, R = resistant.

Table 2. Segregation of chlorate resistance in F_2 populations between *cnx* mutants and wild type IR30 or between *cnx* mutants.

Cross combination	Segregation in F_2 plants ^a			χ^2 value		Probability
	Chlorate-sensitive	Chlorate-resistant	Total plants (no.)	3:1	9:7	
C25/IR30	83	37	120	2.117		0.1 < P < 0.2
C27/IR30	82	34	116	1.149		0.2 < P < 0.3
C32/IR30	83	30	113	0.144		0.5 < P < 0.7
C33/IR30	90	19	109	3.330		0.05 < P < 0.1
C25/C27	102	85	187		0.220	0.5 < P < 0.7
C27/C32	0	198	198	No segregation		
C33/C27	0	168	168	No segregation		

^aThe F_2 seeds were sown in 0.1 mM KC10_3 solution at 30°C . Fourteen days after sowing, chlorate resistance was evaluated visually from the reduction in seedling height and the extent of brown spots on the leaves.